

Kinetic study of micellar effect on the oxidation of Methyl Orange by quinolinium dichromate

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Abstract : The kinetics of oxidation of Methyl Orange (M.O) by quinolinium dichromate (QDC) in perchloric acid medium was studied spectrophotometrically at 510 nm and observed first order dependence on the concentrations of each substrate, oxidant {monomeric form of QDC(QMC)} and acid. Induced polymerization of acrylonitrile was observed. The mechanism involved the attack of the monomeric QDC on the substrate in the rate determining step forming the products. The effect of anionic micelle (SDS) and neutral micelle (TX-100) on the system was studied using Berezin's kinetic model and the binding constant for both the reactants with the micelle have been computed. The Arrhenius equation is verified, and the thermodynamic parameters are determined. A mechanism confirming to the kinetic observations is suggested.

Keywords : Monomeric QDC, Methyl Orange, oxidation, SDS, TX-100, binding constant.

Introduction

Methyl Orange (M.O) is well known dye stuff and is used as a suitable reductant with many oxidants¹. Current interest is on the oxidation of these dyes that adopt the hydrazone tautomeric form, which exhibit much higher oxidation rates. It is known that per acids can oxidize the azo form of dyes to form azoxy compounds². Methyl Orange (M.O) was selected as it is hydrolytically stable in acid media contains no *ortho* substituent and the presence of *para* dimethyl group activates azo group. Subbarao and Murthy³ investigated the oxidation of aromatic azo compounds by peroxy disulphate catalysed by silver, and found to be a chain reaction involving both SO_4^- ion radical and free radicals of the azo compound as chain carriers. Murthy⁴ and coworkers investigated the oxidation of Methyl Orange (M.O) by vanadium(v) and reported that the dye is oxidized to corresponding nitroso compounds following the rupture of -N=N- bond. Murthy⁵ investigated the kinetics of chromic acid oxidation of Methyl Orange. Quinolinium dichromate (QDC) as a Cr^{VI} oxidant was chosen in view of the ease of preparation⁶, stability in the medium selectivity and mild oxidant in synthetic organic chemistry. Mahanti^{7,8} reviewed the syn-

thetic, kinetic mechanistic aspects of complexed Cr^{VI} compounds. The present investigation focuses the attention of the attack of monomeric QDC on the substrate Methyl Orange (M.O) and the formation of products during the course of the reaction involving the rupture of -N=N- bond and the results are discussed in detail in the presence of micelle medium also.

Experimental

All the chemicals were of high grade quality and were used as received without further purification. Quinolinium dichromate (QDC) was prepared by the reported method⁶ and standardized⁹. Its purity was checked by spectral analysis. The infrared spectrum (KBr) exhibited bands at 930, 875, 765 and 730 cm^{-1} , characteristic of the dichromate ion. 0.1% solution of Methyl Orange was prepared by the method given by Vogel¹⁰ and was standardized against a standard titanous chloride solution¹¹. The stock solution is accurately diluted to give a working solution of approximately $1.0 \times 10^{-5} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ as when required. A fluka sample of sodium dodecyl sulphate (SDS) has been used in the preparation of 0.1 mol dm^{-3} solution and its purity was tested by determining the CMC¹²

conductometrically, and has been reported to be $1.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ ^{13,14}. Triton X-100 (TX-100) (Fluka) was cleared of any low-boiling impurities by exposure to vacuum for 3 h at 70 °C following the procedure given by Kumar and Balasubramaniam¹⁵. The CMC of TX-100 has been reported as $2.4 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ ¹⁶. Sodium perchlorate (Fluka) and perchloric acid were used without purification and enabled variation of hydrogen ion concentration at a constant ionic strength (1.0 M).

Kinetic studies :

Kinetic measurements for the oxidation of Methyl Orange were carried out at the absorbance maximum 510 nm as a function of time under pseudo-first order conditions of $[\text{QDC}] \gg [\text{M.O}]$, in acid medium. The reaction was initiated by adding QDC ($2.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$) into the Methyl Orange ($1.0 \times 10^{-5} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$) and perchloric acid (0.2 mol dm^{-3}) system at a fixed ionic strength with sodium perchlorate (0.3 mol dm^{-3}). Absorbance was measured within 45 s by means of Perkin-Elmer Lambda 25 UV/Vis spectrophotometer. The reaction is monitored at different times and log (absorbance) versus time plots are perfectly linear for at least 95% of the reaction. The reactant concentrations have been chosen such that Beer's law is strictly obeyed. The pseudo-first order rate constants were determined from the slopes, in duplicate and found to agree within $\pm 5\%$.

Determination of binding constant of Methyl Orange with SDS and TX-100 micelles :

For determining the binding constants of Methyl Orange (M.O) with SDS micelles at $[\text{H}^+]$ of $2.0 \times 10^{-1} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ and μ at 0.3 mol dm^{-3} is adjusted with NaClO_4 .

Spectra of these substances have been scanned at different SDS concentrations above CMC under the conditions $[\text{SDS}] \gg [\text{M.O}]$ at a wave length of 510 nm, where $[\text{M.O}]$ is $1.0 \times 10^{-5} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$. The results shown that the interaction of Methyl Orange with SDS is negligibly small. The binding constant of Methyl Orange with TX-100 in perchloric acid medium has been reported¹⁷ to be $420 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$.

Determination of binding constant of quinolinium dichromate (QDC) with SDS and TX-100 micelles :

The binding constant values of QDC with SDS micelles at $[\text{H}^+]$ as $2.0 \times 10^{-1} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ and μ at 0.5 mol dm^{-3} under the conditions $[\text{SDS}] \gg [\text{QDC}]$ are determined at 330 nm, for various SDS concentrations. The binding constant of QDC has been found to be $41.0 \pm 0.5 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$. Similar experiments are carried out at different TX-100 concentrations above CMC under the conditions $[\text{TX-100}] \gg [\text{QDC}]$ at 330 nm where $[\text{QDC}]$ is $2.5 \times 10^{-5} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$. The binding constant with respect to TX-100 has been found to be $(1.46 \pm 0.05) \times 10^2 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$.

Results and discussion

To determine the stoichiometry of the reaction a known concentration of QDC ($1.0 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$) was mixed with different concentrations of Methyl Orange $[(0.5-3.5) \times 10^{-5} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}]$ at $[\text{H}^+]$ of 0.2 mol dm^{-3} in water. The reactions were kept overnight for the completion of the reaction and the absorbance was measured at 510 nm. The results confirm that 2 moles of QDC is reacting with 3 moles of Methyl Orange (Scheme 1).

Scheme 1

The reaction products were confirmed as follows. In the case of Methyl Orange 100 mg of substance was mixed with 20.0 ml of 0.1 mol dm⁻³ QDC and 25.0 ml of 5.0 mol dm⁻³ perchloric acid. The reaction mixture was allowed to stand overnight for the completion of the reaction and analysed for products by the following procedure. The products were extracted into ether. The extract was dried with anhydrous calcium carbonate and evaporated in china dish and dissolved in ether. This was tested for the presence of nitroso group by the method suggested by Feigl¹⁸. The oxidizing species Cr^{VI} was reduced to Cr^{III}, which was identified using diphenyl carbazide¹⁹. From the result it was observed that these products did not undergo further oxidation under the present kinetic conditions.

Initiation of vinyl polymerization :

1.5 ml of 0.01 mol dm⁻³ M.O, 3.0 ml of 0.05 mol dm⁻³ QDC and 0.5 ml of 1.0 mol dm⁻³ perchloric acid were kept in the lower limb of a Thunberg tube. In the upper limb 2.0 ml of acrylonitrile were placed. The tube was closed and the air inside the tube was removed by using vacuum pump. Then both the solutions were mixed by shaking the tube. Formation of polymerization was observed. However, a mixture of QDC, acid under these experimental conditions was not found to initiate vinyl polymerization during the time taken for the formation of polymer in the presence of the substrate. The results indicate that the reaction proceed through the formation of a free radical mechanism.

To study the effect of M.O the kinetic runs were carried out under the conditions [QDC] >> [M.O] and plots of log (absorbance) versus time were straight lines for various concentrations of M.O in the range of 0.5 × 10⁻⁵ mol dm⁻³ to 6.0 × 10⁻⁵ mol dm⁻³ (Table 1) showing the first order behavior in M.O. Pseudo-first order rate constants, *k*₁ were evaluated by keeping [QDC] >> [M.O] at different concentrations of QDC from 1.0 × 10⁻³ mol dm⁻³ to 6.0 × 10⁻³ mol dm⁻³ and at constant concentrations of M.O, acid, and ionic strength to study the effect of [QDC]. The plot of *k*₁ versus [QDC] is linear passing through origin at lower [QDC], but deviation from linearity was observed (Fig. 1) at higher [QDC]. The plot of *k*₁ versus [H⁺] is a straight line passing through origin

Table 1. Effect of variation of [M.O], [QDC], [H⁺] on the oxidation kinetics of Methyl Orange by quinolinium dichromate at 298 K and [NaClO₄] = 0.3 mol dm⁻³

[QDC] 10 ³ (mol dm ⁻³)	10 ⁵ [M.O] (mol dm ⁻³)	[H ⁺] (mol dm ⁻³)	10 ⁴ <i>k</i> ₁ (s ⁻¹)
2.0	0.5	0.2	1.18 ± 0.02
2.0	1.0	0.2	1.10 ± 0.04
2.0	2.0	0.2	1.04 ± 0.06
2.0	4.0	0.2	1.04 ± 0.04
2.0	6.0	0.2	1.10 ± 0.03
1.0	1.0	0.2	0.46 ± 0.04
1.5	1.0	0.2	0.71 ± 0.06
2.0	1.0	0.2	0.88 ± 0.08
2.5	1.0	0.2	1.10 ± 0.02
3.0	1.0	0.2	1.28 ± 0.04
3.5	1.0	0.2	1.42 ± 0.06
4.0	1.0	0.2	1.56 ± 0.08
5.0	1.0	0.2	1.90 ± 0.10
6.0	1.0	0.2	2.22 ± 0.04
2.0	1.0	0.05	0.42 ± 0.06
2.0	1.0	0.10	0.61 ± 0.08
2.0	1.0	0.15	0.85 ± 0.06
2.0	1.0	0.20	1.04 ± 0.04
2.0	1.0	0.25	1.74 ± 0.03
2.0	1.0	0.30	2.10 ± 0.02
2.0	1.0	0.35	2.55 ± 0.04
2.0	1.0	0.40	2.68 ± 0.06

showing the first order kinetics with respect to H⁺ ion (Fig. 2) at constant ionic strength (0.3 mol dm⁻³). It was observed that varying ionic strength of the reaction medium has no appreciable effect on the reaction rate.

To study the micellar effect of sodium dodecyl sulphate (SDS) on the rate, the kinetic runs were carried out in the presence of varying concentration of SDS, keeping the concentration of Methyl Orange, QDC and H⁺, μ constant. From the pseudo-first order slopes (Table 2) the specific rate constants *k*₁ are determined and observed a monotonous increase with increase in [SDS]. Kinetic runs were carried out at different concentrations of TX-100 keeping all the reactants and ionic strength as constant. The pseudo-first order rate constants are obtained from log (absorbance) versus time plots. The results (Table 3) show a monotonous increase with increase in [TX-100].

The oxidation of Methyl Orange by QDC was studied

Fig 1. Plot of k_1 versus [QDC] (conditions as in Table 1).

Fig 2. Effect of varying $[\text{H}^+]$ on reaction rate (conditions as in Table 1).

Table 2. Effect of SDS on the oxidation kinetics of M.O by QDC at $[\text{M.O}] = 1.0 \times 10^{-5} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{QDC}] = 2.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{HClO}_4] = 0.2 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{NaClO}_4] = 0.3 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, Temp. = $30 \pm 0.1 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$

$10^2 [\text{SDS}] \text{ (mol dm}^{-3}\text{)}$	$10^4 k_1 \text{ (s}^{-1}\text{)}$
0.0	0.87 ± 0.02
0.2	1.03 ± 0.04
0.4	1.68 ± 0.06
0.8	1.81 ± 0.08
1.2	1.87 ± 0.10
1.6	2.09 ± 0.04
2.0	2.19 ± 0.02
3.0	2.44 ± 0.04
4.0	3.16 ± 0.06
5.0	3.24 ± 0.08
6.0	3.45 ± 0.10

Table 3. Effect of TX-100 on the oxidation kinetics of M.O by QDC at $[\text{M.O}] = 1.0 \times 10^{-5} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{QDC}] = 2.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{HClO}_4] = 0.2 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{NaClO}_4] = 0.3 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, Temp. = $30 \pm 0.1 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$

$10^4 [\text{TX-100}] \text{ (mol dm}^{-3}\text{)}$	$10^4 k_1 \text{ (s}^{-1}\text{)}$
0.0	0.87 ± 0.04
3.4	1.04 ± 0.06
6.8	1.28 ± 0.08
13.6	1.76 ± 0.10
20.4	2.53 ± 0.02
27.2	3.36 ± 0.04
34.0	3.48 ± 0.06
40.8	3.83 ± 0.08
47.6	4.18 ± 0.02

over the temperature range 313 to 333 K and negative values of ΔS^\ddagger provided support for a polar bimolecular reaction. The apparent activation energy from these data has been obtained by using the equation :

$$\ln \frac{k_1(T_2)}{k_1(T_1)} = \frac{E_a}{R} \left[\frac{1}{T_1} - \frac{1}{T_2} \right] \quad (2)$$

$E_a = 67.01$ kJ/mol; $\Delta H = 64.48$ kJ/mol; $\Delta S = -106.65$ J/mol/K; $\Delta G = 97.0$ kJ.

The effect of varying concentration of quinolin on M.O, QDC system was studied at fixed concentration of M.O, QDC and acid. From the results it was observed that quinolinium has no effect on the reaction kinetics. The lack of effect of quinolin on reaction rates rules out the equilibrium from the mechanism.

where QMC = monomeric form of quinolinium dichromate.

The plot of k_1 versus [QDC] is linear passing through origin showing first order kinetics with respect to $[\text{QDC}]_t$. But deviations from linearity are observed at higher $[\text{QDC}]_t$. Under these conditions the kinetic order with respect to QDC is fractional. This bears close resemblance to the pattern observed in the oxidation of Ti^{III} by Ce^{IV} in nitric acid solutions²⁰.

$$\text{Rate} = \frac{d(\text{Ti}^{\text{III}})}{dt} = k(\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}) + k^1(\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}\text{Ti}^{\text{III}}) \quad (4)$$

where k and k^1 are constants and Ce^{IV} is the concentration of monomeric Ce^{IV} . It is well known that dimeric oxidizing species is less reactive than the monomeric form. To find out whether this situation is prevalent in the present reaction also, the author calculated concentration of monomeric form of QDC (QMC) assuming a value²¹ of $35.5 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ dm}^3$ (K_d) for the dimerisation constant for the equilibrium, which is a reported value for aqueous chromic acid system.

The concentration of QMC is calculated using mass

balance.

$$\begin{aligned} [\text{QDC}]_t &= [\text{QDC}] + \frac{[\text{QMC}]}{2} = \frac{2[\text{QDC}] + [\text{QMC}]}{2} \\ &= \frac{2K_d[\text{QMC}]^2 + [\text{QMC}]}{4K_d} \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

or $2K_d[\text{QMC}]^2 + [\text{QMC}] - 4K_d[\text{QDC}]_t = 0$ and

$$[\text{QMC}] = \frac{-1 + \sqrt{1 + 8K_d[\text{QDC}]_t}}{4K_d} \quad (7)$$

The corresponding values of QMC and rate constants are presented in Table 4. The plot of k_1 versus [QMC] (cal-

Table 4. Effect of QMC the oxidation kinetics of M.O by QDC
[M.O] = $1.0 \times 10^{-5} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{HClO}_4] = 0.2 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$,
 $[\text{NaClO}_4] = 0.3 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, Temp. = 30 ± 0.1 °C

10^3 [QMC] (mol dm ⁻³)	$10^5 k_1$ (s ⁻¹)
0.937	4.63 ± 0.04
1.367	7.11 ± 0.06
1.776	8.89 ± 0.08
2.166	11.01 ± 0.02
2.541	12.80 ± 0.04
2.902	14.20 ± 0.06
3.25	15.60 ± 0.08

culated using this procedure) is a good straight line passing through the origin, (Fig. 3) showing that dimeric form of QDC is not the reactive species participating in the mechanism. If dimeric form also reacts the rate law would have assumed the form :

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Rate} &= k_1[\text{QMC}][\text{M.O}][\text{H}^+] \\ &\quad + k_1^1[\text{QDC}][\text{M.O}][\text{H}^+] \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

$$\begin{aligned} &= k_1 \left(\frac{-1 + \sqrt{1 + 8K_d[\text{QDC}]_t}}{2} \right) [\text{M.O}][\text{H}^+] \\ &\quad + k_1^1[\text{QDC}][\text{M.O}][\text{H}^+] \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

According to this, fractional order should have been observed with respect to $[\text{QDC}]_t$ at all conditions. Under the experimental conditions employed all the M.O is in the protonated form HMO^+ ($\text{p}K_a = 3.22$)²².

The H^+ dependence can be explained only by consider-

Fig. 3. Plot of k_1 versus [QMC] (conditions as in Table 4).

ing the protonation of QMC, the protonated form being the reactive oxidizing species. This assumption is justifiable as more electrophilic protonated form of the oxidizing species is known to be always more reactive than the unprotonated form. The mechanism can be represented by the following scheme (Scheme 2).

The scheme leads to the rate law

$$-\frac{d[\text{HMO}^+]}{dt} = k[\text{QMCH}^+][\text{HMO}^+] \quad (11)$$

$$-\frac{d}{dt} [\text{HMO}^+] = kK[\text{QMC}][\text{H}^+][\text{HMO}^+] \quad (12)$$

Scheme 2

where Ar = SO₃HC₆H₄ and Ar^I = COOHC₆H₄

Micellar effect :

The author investigated the micellar effect of the negative micelle (SDS) (Table 2) (Fig. 4) and the neutral micelle (TX-100) (Table 3) (Fig. 6) and found that the reac-

Fig. 4. Plot of k_1 versus [SDS] (conditions as in Table 2).

tion is accelerated by both these micelles. Interestingly TX-100 micelle has greater accelerating effect than SDS micelle. This may be due to the fact that QDC being negatively charged is repelled by the negative SDS micelle to some extent, the binding being only induced by the hydrophobicity, due to the presence of quinolinium moiety. In the TX-100 micelles, the electrostatic repulsive factor is absent and QDC has greater interaction with TX-100 micelles, as shown by the observed binding constant of QDC with TX-100 micelles being greater than with SDS micelles. M.O has been reported to interact with TX-100 appreciably¹⁷. This explains the greater acceleration of TX-100 micelles compared to SDS micelles.

Aqueous chromate or HCrO_4^- is hydrophilic and negatively charged should be repelled by negative SDS micelles. But spectral changes were observed for QDC in the presence of SDS. From the change in the absorbance at 330 nm with change in [SDS-CMC] binding constant for QDC has been found to be $41.0 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$. Simple quinolinium ion has binding constant of $95.5 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$. Attachment of negatively charged HCrO_4^- to QH^+ is responsible for decrease in binding constant from 95.5 to $41.0 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$. No spectral changes were observed for Methyl Orange showing little or no interaction with SDS. But there is some hydrophobicity in the molecule. Therefore very weak interactions, not detected by spectral studies may be possible. The micellar acceleration with both SDS

and TX-100 can be represented by the following scheme.

For the kinetic analysis of the micellar effects, Berezin's model²³ involving the partition coefficient of the species between the micellar and aqueous pseudo phases has been applied. Under the experimental conditions Berezin equation can be written as

$$k_2 = \frac{k_w + k_m K_A P_B C}{(1 + K_A C)(1 + K_B C)} \quad (21)$$

where $k_2 = k_1/[\text{QMC}]$, P_B stands for partition coefficient of M.O and $C = (C_D - \text{CMC})$. K_A and K_B are the binding constant of QDC and substrate with micelle. The value of binding constant K_B with SDS micelles has a negligible value. Hence $K_B C \ll 1$. Accordingly the Berezin equation changes to

$$k_2 = \frac{k_w + k_m K_A P_B C}{1 + K_A C} \quad (21)$$

Taking the value of K_A for QDC with SDS micelle as $41.0 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$, $k_2(1 + K_A C)$ is plotted versus C . A plot

of $k_2(1 + K_A C)$ versus C is linear with a positive intercept (Fig. 5) showing the validity of the rate law and also the accuracy of value for K_A determined by the author.

The intercept corresponds to k_2 ($4.0 \times 10^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ dm}^3$) which is in reasonable agreement with the value of rate constant determination (k_2) in the absence of SDS ($4.35 \times 10^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ dm}^3$). Neutral micelles of TX-100 have greater binding constant with QDC. The binding constant of M.O with [TX-100] above CMC has been reported to be $420 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$ (K_A). Hence, the Berezin

equation assumes that

$$k_2 = \frac{k_w + k_m K_A P_B C}{(1 + K_A C)(1 + K_B C)} \quad (23)$$

Accordingly a plot of $k_2(1 + K_A C)(1 + K_B C)$ versus C where $C = \{[\text{TX}] - \text{CMC}\}$ is a very good straight line with negligible intercept (Fig. 7). This shows that k_w has a value that can be neglected in comparison with that of k_m .

Fig. 5. Plot of $k_2(1 + K_A C)$ versus $\{[\text{SDS}]-\text{CMC}\}$ (conditions as in Table 2).

Fig. 6. Plot of k_1 versus [TX] (conditions as in Table 3).

Fig. 7. Plot of $k_2(1 + K_A C)(1 + K_B C)$ versus $\{[TX]-CMC\}$ (conditions as in Table 3).

Conclusion

The kinetic data and the products obtained in the present investigation demonstrated that the mechanistic path way for the oxidation of Methyl Orange by QDC proceed via free radical mechanism and the rupture of N=N bond by the monomeric quinolinium dichromate (QMC). The effect of micelle on the oxidation reaction can be emphasized basing on the binding constant of each reactant with respect to SDS and Triton X-100 at the described wave length in acid media.

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